

Bioinformatics analysis Luciferase-like Monooxygenase (LLM) from *Priestia megaterium* DSM319 genome

Muhammad Saifur Rohman

Laboratory of Agricultural Microbiology, Faculty of Agriculture, Universitas Gadjah Mada
Jl. Flora, Kompleks Bulaksumur, UGM, Yogyakarta-INDONESIA

Our method to search Luciferase-like monooxygenase (LLM) from *Priestia megaterium* DSM319 genome is done by the following method:

1. By implementing the simple search query method using Boolean queries of NCBI [1]. We change the field of data base into “protein” and then we just type the “Luciferase-like monooxygenase AND *Priestia megaterium* DSM3419” and search. To more clear result we have modify the “default order” to “the organism name” (Figure 1).
2. All the data was downloaded and aligned all the protein sequences by ClustalW [2] and rendered the result by ESPript [3](Figure 2).
3. From the alignment result, it was clearly shown that the sequence identity values were in the range of midnight to twilight zone (10.27-34.56%).
4. To further confirm whether all the sequences are the LLM proteins, we have implemented HHpred [4-5] to test whether the obtained sequences belong to the LLM.

The procedure is schematically shown in Figure 3.

The screenshot displays the NCBI search results page for the query "Luciferase-like monooxygenase AND Priestia megaterium DSM319". The search was performed in the "Protein" database. The results are sorted by organism name and show 10 items. The first five items are listed below:

Item	Protein Name	Accession	GI	Length (aa)
1.	luciferase-like monooxygenase [Priestia megaterium DSM 319]	ADF37657.1	294800591	318
2.	luciferase-like monooxygenase [Priestia megaterium DSM 319]	ADF39478.1	294802412	334
3.	luciferase-like monooxygenase [Priestia megaterium DSM 319]	ADF39497.1	294802431	331
4.	luciferase-like monooxygenase [Priestia megaterium DSM 319]	ADF39648.1	294802582	352
5.	luciferase-like monooxygenase [Priestia megaterium DSM 319]			357

The search details section shows the query: (Luciferase-like monooxygenase[Protein Name] OR Luciferase-like[All Fields] AND monooxygenase[All Fields]) AND ("Priestia megaterium"[organism]).

Figure 1. Interface of the NCBI database. The interface showing how to search the Luciferase-like monooxygenase (LLM) protein in *Priestia megaterium* DSM319 genome. The result indicates that *Priestia megaterium* DSM319 genome contains five LLM proteins.

Figure 2. Alignment of the five LLM sequences from *Priestia megaterium* DSM319 genome. The conserved residues are indicated by red and blue box. The EHH signature is indicated by the red line above the sequence. Alignment was performed by ClustalW and the figure was rendered by ESPript. AAD48477 and AAD48478 are the LuxA and LuxB from *Aliivibrio fischeri*, respectively. ADF39478_1 (LLM1); ADF39497_1 (LLM2); ADF39648_1 (LLM3); ADF40171_1 (LLM4); ADF37657_1 (LLM5). Note: to check the sequence in NCBI database the “_” in accession code must be replaced by “.”.

Figure 3. The procedure for Luciferase-like monooxygenase (LLM) identification from the *Priestia megaterium* DSM319 genome.

References

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